

Exploring quality of life through the lens of sociodemographics and lifestyle behaviour among general population

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Abstract

Quality of life (QoL) is a multidimensional concept influenced by both socio demographic characteristics and individual health-related behaviours. This study aims to understanding how socio-demographic factors and health related behaviours influence QoL is essential for public health interventions. In this study, QoL is assessed using WHO-QoL BREF questionnaire with four domains such as Physical, Psychological, Social and Environmental domains. Nowadays, a significant portion of the population remains unaware of the importance of HRQoL and its determinants, therefore this study is crucial to raise awareness among the general public and guide to future research, as these factors are vitals for daily life and overall well-being throughout the lifespan.

Keywords: Health Related Quality of Life; Socio demographic; Health related behaviours factors; WHO- QoL BREF questionnaire

1. Introduction

Quality of Life (QoL), as defined by the World Health Organization refers to an individual's perception of their position in life. It considers their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns, all within the context of their culture and value systems [1]. QoL indicates how the important way to understand how people feel about their health and daily life. Neglecting HRQoL can lead to worsened physical and mental health, poor treatment adherence, emotional and financial burden on individuals and their families. Measuring the Health-related Quality of life in among general population is important because it helps us compare the quality of life to those with illness and also helps us find out what factors affect HRQoL during the process of healthy or good aging [2].

Quality of life is a subjective part of well being, not a particular and objective one, which makes it hard to assess. Assessment of QoL is essential in clinical and demographic research since it evaluates patient outcome measures. The WHOQoL group has developed a brief assessment scale to measure QoL (WHO BREF), which has demonstrated good reliability and validity in the Indian population as well [12] which are translated into more than 40 languages. These evaluate four separate domains of one's quality of life, we used 26 items where WHOQoL BREF assessment is segmented into physical, psychological, social, environmental domains includes QoL and general health items.

Most socio-demographic factors were significantly associated with HRQoL. Several variables that might affect how people view and report their health, social influences may be particularly significant in determining how people think about their health [3]. Numerous studies indicate that number of socio demographic characteristics, including age, gender, education, income and employment are substantially correlated with HRQoL [3]. In this study, we specially assess how factors such as gender, employment type impact on QoL, as these are crucial influences. While other factors are also important, there are some limitations that prevented us from examining all possible influences in detail.

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Researches which shown that age, marital status, depression, monthly income, relationships and family size influence the QoL of population [13].

Studies indicate health behaviours comprise diverse patterns and smoking drinking or exercising can significantly impact on ADL ability and psychological distress level [14]. Poor health habits such as smoking, drinking excessively and being less physically active result loss of physical capabilities. Some studies indicate that health behaviours are associated with psychological distress. Further more smoking, drinking, increasing screen time, which negatively impact on mental distress [14]. Although our study focused on certain health behaviours such as smoking and alcohol use, it is important to recognize that other factors including physical activity, sedentary behaviour, sleep quality and diet quality also significantly impact on HRQOL.

Objective

To assess the association of QOL between socio-demographic characteristics and health related behaviour.

2. Materials and methodology

A cross sectional study was conducted in the Eraviperoor Grama Panchayat of Pathanamthitta district, Kerala, India. The test run was conducted from November 2023 to April 2024, lasting approximately six months. All patients who, met the inclusion and exclusion criteria were included. Population aged above 15 years, males and females constitute the research study group. The total sample size was 703. The study was initiated after obtaining the approval from the Institutional review board of Nazareth college of pharmacy.

2.1. Inclusion criteria

Patient age above 15 years.

2.2. Exclusion criteria

Individuals who were unwilling to give details. Individuals with cognitive impairments or dementia.

2.3. Data collection method

Data were collected by filling out predesigned data collection forms by making each individual's opinion and their consent with local language. Information was collected through direct, on-site interactions meetings with individuals after obtaining approval from the institutional review board from the Nazareth college of pharmacy. In our study procedure, Participants were first provided with the questionnaire which consist of whoqol – bref questions and after validating the quality of life of the participants we conducted awareness class regarding how to improve the quality of life. The data obtained were statistically analysed to determine the factors which affect the quality of life of general population.

2.4. Statistical analysis

The analysis was performed after entering the data in Microsoft excel – 2013 version, then the result obtained were analysed and represented with graphs and tabulations.

3. Results

Figure 1 Distribution of Gender among general population in the study

The above graph shows that the 703 participants are separated into two genders in which 467 (66.43%) individuals were male and 236 (33.57%) were female.

Figure 2 Distribution of Employment status among general population in the study

The above graph shows that out of the 703 participants, 213 (30.3%) were working, 457 (65.01%) were not working and 33 (4.69%) were retired.

Figure 3 Distribution of Alcohol consumption among general population in the study

Out of the 703 people, the aforementioned graph divides the total population into two groups, alcoholic and nonalcoholic. 28% of the total population were alcoholic and 72% were nonalcoholic.

Figure 4 Distribution of Smoking status among general population in the study

According to the aforementioned graph, the total 703 participants were divided into two groups smokers and nonsmokers. 84% of the total population were nonsmokers and 16% were smokers.

Gender	Physical domain							
	Pain & Discomfort	Energy & Fatigue	Physical Health	Sleep & Rest	Work Capacity	Mobility	Medical Treatment	
M	70.88%	68.84%	67.91%	67.95%	68.67%	67.79%	67.48%	
F	29.12%	3.16%	32.09%	32.05%	31.33%	32.21%	32.52%	
Gender	Psychological Domain							
	Positive Feelings	Learning & Concentration	Body Image & Appearance	Personal Belief	Self-Esteem	Negative Feelings		
M	67.59%	66.86%	68.21%	67.73%	66.82%	70.47%		
F	32.41%	33.14%	31.79%	32.27%	33.18%	29.53%		
Gender	Social Domain							
	Personal Relationships	Social Support	Sexual Activity					
M	66.24%	68.67%	62.71%					
F	33.76%	31.33%	37.29%					
Gender	Environmental Domain							
	Freedom & Physical Safety	Physical Environment	Financial Resources	Opportunity for Leisure Activity	Accessibility to Social Care	Home Environment	Accessibility to Health Care	Transportation
M	69.28%	68.23%	67.84%	66.92%	66.15%	65.88%	65.36%	67.33%
F	30.72%	31.77%	32.16%	33.08%	33.85%	34.12%	34.64%	32.67%

Figure 5 Comparison of Gender and QoL domains based on severity

Smoking behaviour	Physical domain							
	Pain & Discomfort	Energy & Fatigue	Physical Health	Sleep & Rest	Work Capacity	Mobility	Medical Treatment	
U	84.75%	85.27%	84.81%	85.74%	85.03%	84.89%	84.51%	
S	15.25%	14.73%	15.19%	14.26%	14.97%	15.11%	15.49%	
Smoking behaviour	Psychological Domain							
	Positive Feelings	Learning & Concentration	Body Image & Appearance	Personal Belief	Self-Esteem	Negative Feelings		
U	85.19%	84.32%	85.78%	85.61%	85.6%	86.29%		
S	14.81%	15.68%	14.22%	14.4%	14.4%	13.71%		
Smoking behaviour	Social Domain							
	Personal Relationships	Social Support	Sexual Activity					
U	84.15%	86.17%	81.9%					
S	15.85%	13.83%	18.1%					
Smoking behaviour	Environmental Domain							
	Freedom & Physical Safety	Physical Environment	Financial Resources	Opportunity for Leisure Activity	Accessibility to Social Care	Home Environment	Accessibility to Health Care	Transportation
U	86.52%	85.76%	84.38%	84.88%	83.93%	84.36%	84.01%	84%
S	13.48%	14.24%	15.62%	15.12%	16.07%	15.64%	15.99%	16%
	U- Non- smoking				S- Smoking			

Figure 8 Comparison of Smoking behaviour and QoL domains based on severity

4. Discussion

This case study aimed to investigate the relationship between quality of life, backgrounds of individuals and health behaviours. The findings of that study suggest sedentary healthy habits are highly associated with poor quality of life. People with different socio-demographic backgrounds and with unhealthy behaviour such as smoking, alcohol consumption were more likely to report feeling worse across all domains. These results emphasize the role of health and social factors play in determining general well-being. Socio-demographic factors such as gender, and employment along with health-related behaviours alcohol consumption, smoking play a crucial role in determining QoL. Identifying the associations between these factors and QoL can help tailor interventions to specific population groups and improve overall well-being.

In the study conducted by Gaurav Jyani.et.al [15] regarding the gender distribution showed that highest QoL was observed in males (93.6%) and lowest QoL in females (48.8%) which is comparable to our case study reveal women report lower quality of life (33.57%) than men (66.43%). When comparing the four QoL domains, males exhibited higher scores in each domain, indicating a generally better quality of life compared to females (Fig no;5). Women over age of 45 show even lower quality of life compared to younger age groups [5], findings highlight the need for targeted interventions and education programs to improve the quality of life for women due to the combination of several factors such hormonal fluctuations, emotional factors and cor morbidities.

Losing job is one of the stressful life events, which affect people differently [7]. At the same time long term unemployment affects people quality of life, our study found that retired population exhibited lower QoL in all four domains (Fig no; 6) which reveals that potential negative impacts like social isolation, decline in physical health, financial strain. In our study, most participants expressed a lack of interest in their future, often feeling that they were approaching the later stages of life and nearby retirement.

In this study demonstrate that the health- related behaviours such as alcohol consumption and smoking can either improve or diminish a person's quality of life. There is a link between health behaviours and QoL, and it may be bidirectional; positive health behaviours lead to improved QoL, whereas negative health behaviours lead to worse QoL [8]. In our study, we declare a significant correlation between lower quality of life and alcohol consumption, evidence shows that people who drink, even at mild to moderate level, tend to experience a decline in QoL which adversely affect well-being across the four domains (Fig no;7). It is essentially highlighted to recognize the adverse effects of alcohol consumption on various aspects of their lives. In our case study, we found that a higher percentage of people who reported high alcohol consumption also experienced a noticeable impact on quality of life, with increased drinking linked to poorer outcomes across different areas of well-being. Some studies shows that mental health and drinking habits are deeply connected and influenced by emotional struggles, low life satisfaction and psychological distress [9].

Smoking is a major health risk which affects a person's quality of life. Studies have shown that people who smoke often have a lower quality of life [10]. Our case study shows that smoking makes QoL worse and leads to unhealthy behaviours that further affect well-being (Fig no 8). Smoking and higher nicotine dependence are strongly linked to a lower quality of life among general population, highlighting the need for targeted smoking cessation programmes [11].

Our study utilized a semi structured questionnaire and included an awareness component. It became clear from the responses collected that the majority of the participants were unaware about HRQoL and its determinants. We finally conclude that our study showed a significant improvement in the knowledge and awareness about HRQoL among the study participants. Limitation of our study is that we have explored the impact of major socio demographic factors and health related behaviours on HRQoL, yet there can be additional factors determining the HRQoL of the general population and which can be explore for their impact on the HRQoL

Abbreviations

- QoL- Quality of life
- HRQoL- Health Related Quality of Life
- ADL- Activity of Daily Life

5. Conclusion

Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being. Our findings highlight the significant impact of socio-demographic and health related factors on health-related quality of life (HRQoL). Individuals with lower socio-demographic status and poorer health-related behaviors consistently experienced reduced quality of life. These results emphasize the need for targeted interventions that address social and health disparities to improve overall well-being in vulnerable populations. Therefore promoting healthy behaviours and addressing socio-demographic inequalities can lead to improved individual well-being and overall population health.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Romero M, Vivas-Consuelo D, Alvis-Guzman N. Is Health Related Quality of Life (HRQoL) a valid indicator for health systems evaluation? Springerplus. 2013 Dec 11;2(1):664. doi: 10.1186/2193-1801-2-664. PMID: 24353981; PMCID: PMC3866375.
- [2] Levy BR, Slade MD, Kasl SV. Longitudinal benefit of positive self-perceptions of aging on functional health. J Gerontol B Psychol Sci Soc Sci. 2002 Sep;57(5):P409-17. doi: 10.1093/geronb/57.5.p409. PMID: 12198099.
- [3] Jalali-Farahani S, Amiri P, Bakht S, Shayeghian Z, Cheraghi L, Azizi F. Socio-Demographic Determinants of Health-Related Quality of Life in Tehran Lipid and Glucose Study (TLGS). Int J Endocrinol Metab. 2017 Oct 23;15(4):e14548. doi: 10.5812/ijem.14548. PMID: 29344034; PMCID: PMC5750782.
- [4] Jazayeri E, Kazemipour S, Hosseini SR, Radfar M. Quality of life in the elderly: A community study. Caspian J Intern Med. 2023 Summer;14(3):534-542. doi: 10.22088/cjim.14.3.543. PMID: 37520884; PMCID: PMC10379806.
- [5] Didarloo A, Alizadeh M. Health-Related Quality of Life and its Determinants Among Women With Diabetes Mellitus: A Cross-Sectional Analysis. Nurs Midwifery Stud. 2016 Feb 20;5(1):e28937. doi: 10.17795/nmsjournal28937. PMID: 27331054; PMCID: PMC4915209.
- [6] Mulugeta, H., Sinclair, P.M. & Wilson, A. Health-related quality of life and its influencing factors among people with heart failure in Ethiopia: using the revised Wilson and Cleary model. Sci Rep 13, 20241 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-47567->

- [7] Worach-Kardas H, Kostrzewski S. Quality of Life and Health State of Long - Term Unemployed in Older Production Age. *Appl Res Qual Life*. 2014;9(2):335-353. doi: 10.1007/s11482-013-9240-z. Epub 2013 May 17. PMID: 24834137; PMCID: PMC4000620.
- [8] Wu Y, Xu J, Gao Y and Zheng J (2024) The relationship between health behaviors and quality of life: the mediating roles of activities of daily living and psychological distress. *Front. Public Health*. 12:1398361. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2024.1398361
- [9] Pia Mäkelä, Kirsimarja Raitasalo, Kristian Wahlbeck, Mental health and alcohol use: a cross-sectional study of the Finnish general population, *European Journal of Public Health*, Volume 25, Issue 2, April 2015, Pages 225–231, <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/cku133>
- [10] Zhong G, Shu Y, Li H, Zhou Y, Wei Q, Yang B and Yang L (2025) Association between smoking status and health-related quality of life: a study on differences among age groups. *Front. Public Health*. 12:1508236. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2024.1508236
- [11] Rezaei S, Karami Matin B, Kazemi Karyani A, Woldemichael A, Khosravi F, Khosravipour M, Rezaeian S. Impact of Smoking on Health-Related Quality of Life: A General Population Survey in West Iran. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*. 2017 Nov 26;18(11):3179-3185. doi: 10.22034/APJCP.2017.18.11.3179. PMID: 29172297; PMCID: PMC5773809.
- [12] Singh, Abhishek¹; Palaniyandi, Subramani²; Palaniyandi, Anitha³; Gupta, Vikas⁴. Health related quality of life among rural elderly using WHOQOL-BREF in the most backward district of India. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care* 11(3):p 1162-1168, March 2022. | DOI: 10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_1073_21.
- [13] Kim, Sunae, Myoungjin Kwon, and Kawoun Seo. 2022. "Factors Influencing the Health-Related Quality of Life of Workers According to the Type of Work" *Healthcare* 10, no. 10: 2066. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare10102066>.
- [14] Wu Y, Xu J, Gao Y, Zheng J. The relationship between health behaviors and quality of life: the mediating roles of activities of daily living and psychological distress. *Front Public Health*. 2024 May 28;12:1398361. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2024.1398361. PMID: 38864012; PMCID: PMC11165072.
- [15] Jyani G, Prinja S, Garg B, Kaur M, Grover S, Sharma A, Goyal A. Health-related quality of life among Indian population: the EQ-5D population norms for India. *Journal of Global Health*. 2023 Feb 17;13:04018.